

ARCTIC PASSION

Deliverable 4.12

report on development of INFRA as an operational service,
new functionalities and performances.

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ARCTIC
PASSION

Work package

WP 4: Innovating User-Driven Arctic Eurogeo Services

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Executive Summary

In deliverable D4.3, scope and main functionalities of the INFRA service were presented, as developed up to the end of 2023. The present report documents, in Sections 3 and 4, how INFRA's implementation has evolved in the last two years thanks to feedback from users and stakeholders, to enable widespread access to a core set of information as well as to provide additional information. While section 2 aims to give an idea how the dialogue developed, and inputs were collected and used. Evaluation of the social benefit of INFRA, in Section 5, and of the level of use of the Service, in Section 6, provide a way to estimate the “performance” (at least potential) of the INFRA service in its current state. Actions to secure legacy of INFRA, including stakeholder engagement, as well as perspectives arising from connection between wildfires and air quality issues are also presented in Sections 7 through 9.

Although the initial objectives have been achieved and, in some respects, even exceeded, several actions and activities are planned and will also continue to be carried out after the end of the project in a legacy perspective:

- Strengthen dialogue with stakeholders with the aim of activating operational uses of INFRA at level 1 by 2026. At the same time, promote greater awareness and use of level zero, including through the creation of access points in the Arctic (the first one in collaboration with AINA at the KLRS).
- Complete the development of Level 2 of INFRA until it has an operational version that can serve as the basis for specific implementations. Resolve remaining small inconsistencies and instabilities for Level 0 (for example, expand the availability of maps on which to project layers, a set reduced by the sudden closure of some Microsoft services). Improve and expand the system documentation, also taking into account users' suggestions and feedback. In particular, create a small library of use cases.
- Contact services other than GWIS, in particular the Canadian CWFIS and the American National Interagency Fire Center, to explore how, through specific agreements, the information available in INFRA can be enriched, particularly for levels 1 and 2. The only important limitation being to always and only interact with well-certified public sources.
- Fully develop interaction with the AURORAE service, including information layers on fire emissions, particularly those from CAMS GFAS. We should also explore broader synergies on air quality, including the use of INFRA's capabilities to transfer information beyond fire emissions.

List of Abbreviations

AINA	Arctic Institute of North America
AMF	Arctic Mayor's Forum
AURC	Arctic Urban regional Cooperation (network)
AURORAE	Air qUality foRecast fOR Arctic communitiEs (service)
BOLAM	BOlogna Limited Area Model: hydrostatic numerical weather prediction model at limited area
CAMS	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service
CAMS GFAS	The CAMS Global Fire Assimilation System
CAP	Common Alerting Protocol
CNR-ISAC	Consiglio Nazionale Ricerche–Institute of Atmospheric Sciences and Climate
CWFIS	Canadian Wildland Fire Information System
EEAS	The European External Action Service (of EU Commission)
FRP	Fire Radiative Power
FTPS	File Transfer Protocol over Secure Socket Layer
GWIS	Global Wildfire Information System
HTTPS	'HyperText Transfer Protocol over Secure Socket Layer
IAOAF	International Arctic Observing Assessment Framework
INFRA	INtegrated Fire Risk mAnagement
INFRA-AEGIS	INFRA CAE Geospatial Information System
INFRA-SENTRY	INFRA – web-based dissemination platform
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
JRC	Joint Research centre (Ispra)
KLRS	Kluane Lake Research Station
MODIS	Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer
MODIS-LCM	MODIS Land Cover Type 1
MOLOCH	MOdel LOCal: non-Hydrostatic numerical weather prediction model at limited area
NC-FTM	New Canadian Fuel Type Map
netCDF	Network Common Data Form
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
NWP	Numerical Weather Prediction model
OASIS	Organization for the Advancement of Structured Information Standards

PM10	particulate matter with an aerodynamic diameter less than or equal to 10 micrometers
PRA	Italian Arctic Research Program
RNA CoObs	Research Networking Activity for Coordinated Arctic Observations
SAON	Sustaining Arctic Observing Network
SAV	Shared Arctic Variable
SBA	Social Benefit Area
SLCFs	Short Lived Climate Forcers
US AON	United States Arctic Observing Network
VCA	Value Chain Analysis
VTA	Value Tree Analysis
XML	Extensible Markup Language
WMO	World Meteorological Organization

1. Introduction

Deliverable D4.3 presented the objectives underlying the development of the INFRA (INtegrated Fire Risk mAnagement) service, as well as the features planned and developed for it by the end of 2023. The same deliverable also reports about the intense dialogue with potential users and stakeholders, particularly with Arctic communities, as a fundamental element in the development of the service. This dialogue has continued to develop over the past two years, leveraging

(i) the opportunities offered by the calendar of events that annually bring together the polar scientific community and/or aim to engage the scientific world with representatives of communities, politics, and the business world

and, more proactively,

(ii) the opportunities created by the project itself, from the General Assembly (GA - particularly the 2024 one held at Inari-Finland), to the meetings of expert groups discussing the wildfires topic in the Shared Arctic Variable (SAV) context.

(iii) participation in specific meetings, such as the conference organized by AINA in February 2024 in Calgary and the specific session held during the GA of the RNA CoObs project at the end of August 2024.

(iv) webinars organized to present INFRA and its features, or to discuss the potential interaction/integration of services related to wildfires and air quality.

The overall outcome of this dialogue strongly influenced and drove the INFRA service's development and consolidation efforts over the past two years.

This report documents how INFRA's implementation has evolved thanks to the feedback from this dialogue, to enable widespread access to a core set of information as well as to provide additional information. Section 3 and 4 are dedicated to that. While section 2 aims to give an idea how the dialogue developed, and inputs were collected and used. Evaluation of the social benefit of INFRA, in Section 5, and the level of use of the Service, in Section 6, provide a way to estimate the “performance” (at least potential) of the INFRA service in its current state. Actions to secure legacy of INFRA, including stakeholder engagement, as well as perspectives arising from connection between wildfires and air quality issues are also presented in Sections 7 through 9.

2. Lessons learned: what input from stakeholders and potential users

Beyond what was said in the introduction, it is certainly useful to report, even if only briefly, how the dialogue with stakeholders and users has actually developed and how it has subsequently led to the developments we will discuss in detail in the next section. We focus on three events and opportunities due to their relevance.

Workshop in Calgary February 2024

During February a three-day workshop “**Building Resilience to Mountain Wildfires by Weaving Indigenous and Scientific Ways of Knowing**” was jointly organized by the Canadian Mountain Network and Arctic Institute of North America. The workshop brought together diverse Sure thisexperts to improve understanding of mountain wildfires by integrating Indigenous and scientific knowledge systems to enhance community resilience.

Along with representatives from academic institutions, representatives from eight indigenous nations and three indigenous societies participated in the work and formulated the final recommendations included in a report available from the institutions that organized the event.

Of the three broad themes covered, the third was of particular importance to us, regarding "*How can observation, monitoring, information management, and new forms of constructive partnership help to build wildfire resilience?*"

The large and qualified representation of indigenous nations and societies particularly highlighted a strong desire to be more involved in decision-making and management processes. They also expressed their regret that their centuries-old knowledge base on land management in relation to wildfires is poorly followed/utilized.

The need to better communicate information, making users active participants rather than just passive end-users, was the lesson learned from trying to present our service and its potential. Another lesson learned was to seek to reach and inform individuals, not just institutions, in order to build over time a relationship of trust in the information provided by science and allow for its better inclusion and use within the knowledge and needs of each Arctic Indigenous person.

The three days offered a valuable insight into the needs of the Indigenous peoples of the Canadian Arctic, and the discussion was at times not at all easy, having to overcome barriers of values and sensitivity regarding this and other issues.

Among the insights gained, there was also the need to create the right conditions to allow individuals and communities time to discover, at their own pace and in their own ways, the benefits and ways to use the service effectively.

The results of this workshop represented a turning point and provided the definitive impetus to embrace a multilevel approach (see section 3) with the goal of making the end user more active and not just passive in communicating information about the situation at hand, whether it was a risk or an ongoing event, and using this information to better respond.

[Arctic PASSION General Assembly in Inari June 2024](#)

The General Assembly, held in Inari a few months after the Calgary conference, was crucial because it allowed us to present the results of our work and the changes made to INFRA to both the project community and local Sami and potential users, receiving their feedback. The approach to the General Assembly and the creation of an exhibition area also facilitated this discussion, as it presented us with the need to develop a simple yet effective way to showcase INFRA's functionality and potential.

Although external participation was less than we had hoped, the internal discussion with academic colleagues and indigenous representatives was very positive.

The simplicity and ease of use of the platform at its level zero was particularly appreciated, as was the amount of additional information that level 2 could provide thanks to its higher spatial resolution.

Among the input received was the request to simplify and unify access and, above all, better document the service, its functionality, and its potential uses. Several people reiterated the absolute need to find a good connection between the INFRA service and the ARORAE air quality service developed by colleagues at the JRC in Ispra.

It's noteworthy that interest in the work being carried out has also extended to the educational level. Indeed, our group committed to provide GRID-ARENDAL with the necessary materials for a

summer school that the Tahltan community was organizing for children and adolescents on two crucial topics: the dynamics and fate of ice and wildfires in an era of climate change. The school's input allowed us to provide a concrete response to the request received, to better document INFRA, all the underlying work and the scientific basis behind it in the most accessible way possible.

Like in the case of Calgary, we immediately sought to respond to the requests and input received. A web page was set up to access all INFRA implementations, and the same page was used to provide access to a significant amount of documentary material. Great effort, especially in documentation (see next sections for details).

[INFRA and AURORAE Joint webinar May 2025](#)

The webinar “*Wildfires and Air Quality Forecasting - Services Features & Users' Feedbacks*” jointly organized by CNR and JRC Ispra, was extremely important to give an idea of the impact the two services can provide, particularly when combined. The main inputs in this case arose from the Tahltan and from the Cree (Eeyou Nation) representatives.

The most important message from this webinar is the extreme interest of Canada's indigenous peoples in the combined issue of wildfires and air quality. It was again stressed that communication on these issues is poorly targeted and of little use to end users who are not experts in the field. Many products are used—too many, for sure. Chiefly, those tasked with gathering information and conveying it to end users receive little guidance from experts, and the available products are designed for all potential users without any specific adaptation work for indigenous peoples and their unique conditions and needs.

The commitment, in the coming months, is to try to develop a response to these inputs and lessons learned. Some discussions took place before the summer, but other priorities then took precedence over the summer months. However, meetings and concrete plans are scheduled for the winter with the specific goal of discussing solutions and products tailored to their needs with Tahltan and Eeyou representatives, in order to make good use of the skills and knowledge that CNR and JRC Ispra have on these specific topics

3. Improving Implementation of INFRA

In developing a new wildfire service, as mentioned already in deliverable D4.3, two fundamental questions need to be addressed:

- 1 - How can the new service distinguish itself from other information channels and from existing services and activities carried out by organizations/individuals that often perform this task based on a political, legal, or administrative mandate (from the territory, emergencies, etc.).
- 2 - Having identified its usefulness and unique features, how can we ensure that it complements existing services, with positive effects and avoiding confusion and overlap.

To the first question, we responded by developing a service that simplifies access to relevant information and products on wildfires and makes it possible to transform, integrate, and disseminate such information, focusing on a local scale. This will ensure that non-experts can more easily obtain what they need from this information at a given moment.

But, once INFRA's overall objective was identified, answering the second question was less

straightforward. Based on the input and information gathered, our answer evolved significantly during the project.

The initial idea was to create a service that would involve some "expert" responsible for carrying out this transformation, inclusion, and dissemination to end users. Figure 9 of deliverable D4.3 reflects this vision of a service in which the core IT platforms, INFRA-AEGIS and INFRA-SENTRY, are used and managed in combination by a "control room," where an expert interprets and integrates the information accessed by INFRA-AEGIS. The same expert and the same "control room" then transform the information, prepare tailored text messages (addable image files), and disseminate them according to pre-established plans, determined by appropriate initialization of INFRA-SENTRY (see D4.3 - Appendix 1). In this vision, the operational implementation of INFRA relies on a system of credentials that experts and the "control room" must possess, credentials that authorize them to operate. Although the use of a cloud computing environment makes this "control room" concept very lightweight and relocatable to the most appropriate and suitable location, the INFRA service, as envisioned until the end of 2023, did not consider free access and use. Its operational implementation required human resources and the necessary interest of a party with the authority and responsibility to serve a population, community, municipality, or territory.

3.1. The multi-level approach

The meeting in Calgary (February 2024) clearly highlighted that the barrier represented by access credentials does not allow to fully exploit the intrinsic nature of INFRA: simplify access to relevant information and products on wildfires, making them available to a variety of end-users through simple platforms and tools. Obviously, removing the credential and expert barrier necessarily implies giving up some features and information.

Therefore, we began to consider the possibility of having different access methods to INFRA. This new approach was presented at the INARI 2024 General Assembly, where the interest in and usefulness of having different levels of implementation were evident. Hence, we continued along this line, seeking to also pay greater attention to the products and information to be made immediately available to end-users, as well as to the quality of the documentation accompanying the basic level of the service. Section 3.2 focuses on these latter issues of proper documentation of the service and training on its use.

A multi-level approach to the operational implementation of the INFRA service allows for the satisfaction of all different needs and the ability to leverage both ways in which information can be handled and transferred:

LEVEL 0: At this level, the INFRA service is completely open and accessible to anyone with a computer and sufficient internet bandwidth to comfortably use and navigate the INFRA-AEGIS web-mapping platform. This level is therefore intended for general users, and the amount of information is as appropriate as possible for their limited expertise. To assist these users, we put great attention to the level of documentation (see section 3.2). The frequency of information updating is clearly linked to the sources, usually daily for risk indices (vegetation status, ignition), 6-8 hours for information related to active fires and burned areas.

Implement INFRA: a level approach to serve different users

LEVEL ZERO

(not expert users)

- A FREE accessible web-GIS platform (INFRA-AEGIS) implemented on a computer cloud infrastructure.
- Information currently from GWIS (easy to add more)
- Friendly and intuitive functionalities, aiming to give emphasis to the local scale.

AMONG FUNCTIONALITIES:

Evaluation of distances and areas; quick zoom; export map as image.

LEVEL ONE:

(reserved to who have role and responsibilities)

- Integrated use of INFRA-AEGIS and another IT platform (INFRA-SENTRY) to elaborate tailored textual messages and distribute them to a great variety of end users.
- simple mask to introduce information, write a text, associate images
- high flexibility in defining contacts, groups of users, distribution profiles
- Possibility to introduce processes (executable, batch, etc.)
- in the distribution profile (for example to activate automatically a mechanical/electronic system as a rele')

Level 1 requirements are till suitable to directly involve small actors

LEVEL TWO:

(need "expert" and budget resources)

- Products generated also by INFRA thanks to a computational module.
- Need to support routine running of an high resolution (1.2 km) numerical weather prediction model (NWP).
- A local (not cloud) computing implementation can be considered.

Figure 1.- A synthesis of different levels to which INFRA can be implemented from an operational point of view. Also indicated are some main characteristics, as well as end-users that can be served and necessary resources level.

LEVEL 1: At this level, the INFRA-AEGIS platform is complemented by the INFRA-SENTRY platform, which allows authorized personnel to prepare text messages for distribution to end users through channels such as phone calls, text messages, social media, etc. The message is prepared by the operator/expert using a dedicated dashboard. INFRA-SENTRY then translates the text message into a digital format according to the CAP standard protocol.

The Common Alerting Protocol (CAP) is an international standard for emergency alerting and public warning systems. It's a digital format that allows for consistent alert messages to be disseminated across multiple communication systems, ensuring that critical information reaches the public effectively and efficiently. CAP is designed to be adaptable for all types of hazards and can be used with various media platforms (ITU, 2025; WMO, 2025; NOAA, 2025). Developed by the Organization for the Advancement of Structured Information Standards (OASIS), and adopted by many, CAP uses a standardized, XML-based format, making it easy to implement and ensuring interoperability between different systems. Among the most interesting CAP features for our purposes is the ability to associate images with the textual message with a resolution suitable for the channel we are using to distribute information to end users.

In deliverable D4.3, we have already provided many details on INFRA-SENTRY, and in the appendix, we also provided the list of information necessary to initialize and make this platform operational in a specific situation. In addition to its great flexibility and the large number of channels that can be activated for distribution, other aspects of INFRA-SENTRY are important to highlight: (i) the possibility to make available in the dashboard pre-packaged message templates, and then easily prepare the message in a repetitive format easily recognizable and interpretable over time by users; (ii) the ability to insert simple

commands that can be highly effective remotely. This latter functionality can be, for example, used to change the state of a relay and thereby cutting off power to a system, closing a valve, and much more.

This level doesn't require significantly different IT resources than level zero. The real difference is that it's used by personnel/organizations with institutional responsibilities for managing and communicating alerts. Hence the need to implement it with credential-based access. **When the message is prepared, in addition to information on the status of fires and associated risks, it's certainly possible to introduce specific information and alerts derived from the local situation, particularly knowledge of the specific needs of the users being addressed, whether temporary or structural. An important additional way to tailor the message to user needs.**

LEVEL 2: At this level, the INFRA service provides both the outputs of a high-resolution weather forecasting model developed at the CNR, MOLOCH, and a computational module. Through this module, INFRA calculates various risk parameters at the forecasting model's 1.25 km resolution. This level significantly increases the information made available to the operator. Meteorological information in the messages can complement the information distributed through INFRA-SENTRY. MOLOCH's forecast does not extend beyond 48 hours, but its current advantage is its spatial resolution, which can make a significant difference at a local scale. The price to pay for this additional information is the need not only for an experienced operator, but also for the financial cost of using the numerical forecasting model (NWP) for a specific area. The simplest solution, of course, is to entrust the task to a specialized center and/or research lab. The NWP model code is open and available. Once again, the solution adopted offers the greatest possible flexibility. Details on MOLOCH are available in deliverable 4.3 and on the CNR-ISAC websites (CNR-ISAC, 2025).

A schematic summary of all information provided above for levels 0,1 and 2, is provided in Figure 1.

ABOVE LEVEL 2: Figure 9 in deliverable D4.3 indicates how an integrated fire service can and should leverage surface observations, as well as satellite observations and assessments that are ultimately model-based. Actively involving users in increasing the flow of information can yield significant benefits at a local scale, providing valuable information to better understand what is happening in real time and to better prepare the content of the messages to be distributed.

Depending on the specific implementation and use of INFRA, early warnings may also be considered. INFRA's capabilities could, in this case, be leveraged to provide new ways of integrating information from automatic ground observation systems/networks, human observation networks, and individual reports at the local level. From the local level, this could be extended to larger scales.

Being INFRA developed to be implemented and used in local contexts and by entities, both public and private, operating at these scales, it is particularly suitable for bespoke uses. Due to the unique nature of each individual development in this regard, we have not yet developed any use case, either at an operational or demonstration level. However, the potential has been analyzed, and the results of this technical analysis can serve as a starting

point should any potential users express interest in exploring the topic further.

3.2. Documenting the service and training users

The introduction of INFRA's Level 0 implementation brings with it a greater need to properly document and illustrate not only INFRA's features, but also the best way to use these features to properly interpret the available information and use it individually or in combination.

With this in mind, we decided to focus primarily on a sufficiently detailed video tutorial, dedicated to describing not only the features but also the meaning of the different information levels produced, and finally demonstrating their possible integrated use in specific examples related to real events. Therefore, the video tutorial is divided into three fairly distinct and identifiable parts. The resulting product lasts over 20 minutes and is made available not only online on the INFRA implementations info page, but also downloadable under a Creative Commons license. This increases the possibility for the video tutorial to be accessed offline, revisited as needed, and even manipulated and adapted to specific situations (always with the restriction of non-commercial use). To fully demonstrate the three-chapter structure of the tutorial, it is available for download in its entirety, or by separating parts 1 and 2 from part 3.

The existence of Level 0 also requires providing explanations of how the INFRA service was developed and how the information presented is generally obtained from observations, particularly satellite observations. Obviously, the communication strategy also includes the webinars that have illustrated the service and its objectives during the project, and a survey developed in conjunction with the air quality service. Such survey was also designed to provide feedback that users can leave at their leisure, thus providing information that grows over time.

The documentation is completed by an information page on the various layers found in the INFRA implementations (both levels) and a detailed explanation of the legends. Unfortunately, these legends, often linked to the layers retrieved from GWIS, are not easily simplified. Therefore, they must be carefully explained. At the moment, this last part of the documentation is the only one missing and under development. We'll discuss this material further in Section 6, and how it was made available with the project's legacy in mind.

4. New products

4.1. The vegetation stress index

During drought events, vegetation canopy can be affected by water stress. This can have major impact on plant development in general and can cause a strong increase in fire risk. Therefore, recognition of plant water stress status can provide a very useful fire risk index. Nowadays, satellite observations offer a good opportunity to evaluate such an index on a near-real time basis, considering that several optical indices we can retrieve using satellite sensor observations are strongly related to the plant water content. They are therefore a very good proxy for plant water stress.

In the frame of INFRA we are working to develop an automated method for mapping on a daily basis the level of vegetation water stress, using 500-m Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS), making it possible to identify pixels potentially under fire risk. Work is in progress and will be completed even after the end of the project and implemented in level 2.

4.2. Fuel maps

The characterization and mapping of fuel types are among the most critical aspects of the process of developing accurate wildfire propagation models.

Working on INFRA, we dedicated great attention to this topic, with the aim of increasing the frequency at which the map file can be updated. For that, a MODIS-Based Approach for Annual Updating of Fuel Type Maps in the Canadian Fire Behavior Prediction System, was developed. The new methodology proposed for peer review in Nestola et al. (2024). Using this methodology, updated fuel type maps can be generated on an annual base, by associating land cover classes derived from the MODIS (Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer) MCD12Q1 product with fuel classes defined by the Canadian Fire Behavior Prediction (FBP) System. Below, we report a brief description of what was developed, leaving to the above reference the duty to provide more details on developed methodology as well as its performance.

About data, the method uses those provided by the MODIS Land Cover Type 1 (MODIS LCM) product covering all of Canada, along with the official FBP Fuel Type Map (FBP FTM) as a reference. Both datasets were reclassified into a new fuel type map, termed the New Canadian Fuel Type Map (NC-FTM), which includes seven main classes.

The developed methodology consists of three key phases:

1. adaptation of MODIS-LCM and FBP FTM data to ensure consistent classification across Canada;
2. resolution of ambiguities between classes using semantic and ecological compatibility criteria;
3. validation of the new fuel-type classification through accuracy analysis based on a confusion matrix.

As for results, the classifier's accuracy analysis yielded a value exceeding 85%, confirming the reliability of the proposed method. Comparisons between the reclassified maps showed strong consistency between MODIS land cover classes and the fuel types predicted by the FBP system.

The proposed approach, based on medium-resolution MODIS data, is effective, cost-efficient, and replicable. Thanks to MODIS's annual updates, this methodology enables regular fuel type map revisions, enhancing the predictive and operational capabilities of the FBP model. So, this method provides an operational solution for the annual classification of fuel types across Canada. Moreover, the procedure can be adapted to other boreal regions, supporting wildfire planning, prevention, and management efforts.

5. Assessing Social Benefit of INFRA

Assessing the social benefit of the services being developed was a key activity of the Arctic PASSION project. WP5 of the project was entirely dedicated to advancing the development of a methodology suitable for this purpose, and then using this methodology to attempt to determine the social benefit associated with the various services. The methodology and tools developed during the project are extensively illustrated in deliverable D5.2, which provides a sort of guidebook. While a general framework can be developed based on qualitative and then quantitative assessments (see D5.2, figure 5, page 13) involving both developers and end users, its development varies from case to case. Deliverable D5.3 reports the results of all the analysis and evaluation work on the eight services developed by Arctic PASSION, and therefore also for INFRA. In the case of INFRA, the evaluation focused solely on qualitative aspects, determined both by a basic qualitative understanding of impacts from a developers' perspective (Value Chain Analysis - VCA) and by a qualitative assessment from the end-users' perspective (in preliminary form). Figure 2 shows the VCA result, reproducing Figure 22 of deliverable D5.3.

Figure 2.- The Value Chain Analysis (VCA) for the Arctic Service INFRA.

Value Tree Analysis (VTA) is one of the tools developed in WP5 to help monitor and trace potential impacts of observation services that do not stem from the economic background. In the case of INFRA, however, the VTA was carried out not only using the tools developed by Arctic PASSION, but also in cooperation with US AON (Arctic Observing Network) and its Benefit Tool (US AON, 2025). Indeed, US AON, within the context of SAON, has interacted extensively with Arctic PASSION on this aspect and is developing a VTA for each of the eight Arctic services. Figure 3 shows the VTA framework developed by US AON.

Figure 3.- US AON's Benefit Tool provides a systematic way to link observing system inputs, through intermediate products and applications, to the societal benefit areas they support. The line thickness conveys the relative importance of each underlying input to the product, application, or benefits..

The tool developed by AON is primarily based on the logic models and categories developed by Meadow and colleagues (Meadow et al., 2021). A spreadsheet helps to collect all the information needed to create the database that allows for the construction of a graphical representation of the VTA. For both US AON and the Arctic PASSION project, the reference framework for building this VTA is The International Arctic Observing Assessment Framework (IAOAF, IDA, 2017). IAOAF provides a comprehensive, consistent, and cross-sectoral view of value delivery from the Arctic observing systems to Arctic-specific Societal Benefit Areas (SBAs). The IAOAF identifies 12 relevant societal benefit areas, further specified into 42 sub-areas and 140+ key objectives. A key aspect of the US AON framework is the categorization of social impacts.

Figure 4.- The five categories of societal impacts used by US AON's Benefit Tool..

The five categories identified and used are shown in Figure 4. It is important to note here that, compared to this classification, the INFRA service can impact four of these categories. The only

one excluded, not surprisingly, is instrumental applications, as INFRA is a service that essentially collects, integrates, transforms, and distributes existing information.

6. Use of INFRA service

As described in the previous sections, the development of INFRA, its functionalities, and, above all, the amount of information made available, continued throughout 2024. Therefore, although the service had been implemented at least for the Alaska/Canada test area by late 2023, the constant changes and updates made it difficult to use. Furthermore, until mid-2024, the multi-level approach had not been fully developed, and therefore access to INFRA could only be achieved by displaying and using credentials. In the second half of 2024, level 0, accessible to any user with an internet connection, became available. During the same period, intense work was carried out on developing both the documentation and the single access page on the PRA portal. As the service gradually consolidated its development, it was possible to launch a more vigorous dissemination effort among potential users, as well as discussions with project partners such as AINA regarding coordinated actions to promote the service. The webinars organized in early 2025 and then in the spring together with the air quality service (described in the previous section), allowed us to reach some new users and expand our knowledge of INFRA. Even if just started, and with some small adjustments planned, looking at access statistics can be useful to assess the level of awareness the service has reached and begin to glimpse its potential. We're talking about level 0, accessible to all. For levels 1 and 2, the promotion and the search for interested rights holders and stakeholders—be they indigenous communities, municipalities, or small organizations—is ongoing, and more actions are planned for next months of 2025 and also 2026. Website Access Statistics reported in the table and figures below refer to the period 1 January to 30 June 2025

Considering that we are in a starting phase of the INFRA service, and that we can still consider it as a testing phase, it makes no sense to deepen the analysis too much. We will only focus on a couple of Key indicators such as Total number of accesses to the service (total visits) and geographic distribution. These basic metrics can at least provide a rough idea about the level of knowledge and interest in the INFRA service and the degree of geographical coverage achieved. Table 1 provides these indicators for the three test areas.

Table 1. Summary of Key Metrics (6 months 2025)

Area of interest	Geographic Distribution Visits	Total Visits
Alaska	15	258
Fennoscandia	14	150
Sakha-Yakutia	15	149

Figures 5,6, and 7 below show the percentage of visits per period from January to end of June 2025 for three areas of interest. In this way we can detail the geographical coverage and the relative contribution to total visits originating from each country.

Figure 5: Geographic distribution access trend percentage from January to June 2025: Alaska.

Figure 6: Geographic distribution access trend percentage from January to June 2025: Fennoscandia.

Figure 7: *Geographic distribution access trend percentage from January to June 2025: Sakha-Yakutia.*

Before closing this section, it's important to note that the geographic distribution of access to Fennoscandia also includes users who connected from Russia. Obviously, since level zero is open, it cannot impose limits on access based on geographic regions, and therefore, if necessary, we must address potential regulations in this regard. We believe this is a paltry compromise to the benefit of better serving all Arctic communities.

7. Securing INFRA after the end of Arctic PASSION

A truly important point concerns the legacy of the work done within the project and the long-term support of the INFRA service developed. Sustainability was a key criterion that strongly guided the overall development, as were the choices we had to make from time to time: sustainability of its use by the most diverse users, as well as sustainability of its operation after the Arctic PASSION project is concluded. The solutions and choices to ensure the former are largely reported in section 3, as well as in deliverable 4.3. These same choices and approaches are also very useful for operational sustainability. Specifically, this is made less complicated and costly by two elements: 1) the multi-level approach and 2) implementation in a cloud computing environment. The second aspect necessarily entails the need to create implementations that are sufficiently independent from the IT environment in which they are located. The structure of the AEGIS and SENTRY platforms that constitute the IT core of the service has made it easy to achieve the necessary level of autonomy and eliminated the need to connect to dedicated libraries and software. The service is therefore easily exportable from the cloud computing environment where it is currently installed and transportable to proprietary machines, thus reducing costs and gaining greater freedom to use storage resources (very expensive in cloud systems). Finally, the same multi-level approach, as mentioned, can contribute to operational sustainability, because INFRA can be kept operational at the level appropriate to interest and resource availability. Level 0 can actually cost very little if the service is based in a suitable location.

Thanks also to the relatively modest needs mentioned above, the CNR and its polar structure are certainly capable of ensuring the functionality and operability of the service, leveraging the IT resources that also support the Italian polar repositories. In addition, the portal of the Italian Arctic Research Program (PRA) offers a useful complement and alternative to the Arctic PASSION webpage, providing access to all the implementations completed to date and to the documentation, particularly that developed for the best possible use of level zero. Creating a single access point on a page that guarantees continuity, being somewhat institutional, certainly ensures that it will be possible in the future not only to maintain the service but also to highlight new developments, new features, and new implementations that hopefully will arise from the interest of potential users. The INFRA page is accessible at www.programmaricercaartico.it/

8. Engaging stakeholders, connecting with Aurorae service

Now that the INFRA service has reached a good level of development maturity and consolidated its two fundamental characteristics, namely

- (i) attention to non-expert users and local conditions, and
- (ii) flexibility of use by a broad range of stakeholders without requiring significant resource commitments,

the real challenge is to promote its use. The difference between levels 0, 1, and 2 of the service in terms of the users it aims to reach and to serve makes it necessary to address this aspect differently.

Promoting level 0 primarily requires providing potential users with documentation that is simple to understand but also effective in helping them comprehend, as independently as possible, its potential uses, the information that can be acquired, and how to integrate it with other information sources, including those that users can collect locally. In this regard, producing a video tutorial seemed a priority, and we worked hard to realize it. Not only is it accessible online, but it can also be downloaded locally, making it easier to learn and encourage people to find their own ways of interpreting the information provided by the service, ways that can be tied to specific needs and/or curiosity.

The use approach proposed is not far from that applied to weather forecasting. This is because, conceptually, we're addressing the same issue: understanding the current situation and using this improved understanding to act and/or to respond to needs and requests with greater awareness. In the case of weather forecasts, people have now become accustomed to searching for and checking them regularly, even when the situation is such that there's little need. This continuity has undoubtedly increased awareness of potential risks. Something similar can be promoted and sought for fires as well. And the INFRA service, at its Level 0 level, can be effective in this regard.

An important aspect is represented by the user feedback. A dedicated survey was prepared in collaboration with the partners who developed the air quality service and implemented it on the SLIDO platform. It is available/accessible from the INFRA website.

While the internet remains the primary channel for promoting INFRA, with an increasingly detailed website and webinars developed and made available, an effective tool could be to set up on-site access points providing printed materials, and where trained staff is available to explain service

use, also through practical examples. In September 2024, an exploratory tour was conducted for this purpose in Yukon at the Kluane Lake research station (KLRS), managed by AINA. In the coming months, we intend to work on implementing a first access point in that location. We will select, in cooperation with AINA, what is suitable among the material we have available, and will integrate it according to the recommendations of those who work at KLRS. We will also train station staff, so that they will be able to stimulate users, respond to questions/requests, and promote the collection of user feedback. This last feature enables the possibility to continue to make the service increasingly useful by adding new information and improving documentation/examples of use.

For levels 1 and 2, the promotion strategy necessarily involves identifying specific stakeholders among those who govern and manage the territory, approaching and soliciting them individually, promoting dedicated meetings in which not only the service is illustrated, but, once the specific needs are understood, ad hoc implementations can be proposed. INFRA's flexibility in adding information to the package designed so far and in generating messages tailored to specific needs should facilitate this. We have not yet received any requests for these levels, but we have ongoing contacts with representatives of a couple of Canadian First Nations, the Tahltan in British Columbia and the Cree (Eeyou Nation) in Quebec, in addition to contacts established with the Gwich'in since the preparatory phase of the proposal. Dialogue with Tahltan and Cree initiated after their participation in the webinars organized throughout 2025 as part of Arctic PASSION activity, demonstrating that these events can be truly useful when reaching these types of stakeholders.

Two webinars have been organized: the first, relating solely to the INFRA service, was held in February 2025, and the second, in cooperation with the AURORAE air quality service, was held in May 2025. Both webinars can be accessed from the Arctic Passion website, as well as the PRA portal page. However, the best resource is an information page at everyone's disposal on the JRC website (JRC, 2025). Our plan is to organize in fall a webinar aimed not only at indigenous communities but also at some municipalities. To this scope, we have been (and continue to be) in contact with both the Arctic Mayor's Forum (AMF) and the AURC network, an initiative promoted by the European Community.

Arctic Urban Regional Cooperation (AURC) is an initiative focused on enabling local authorities in Arctic countries to collaborate on sustainable urban and regional development. It facilitates peer-to-peer learning and knowledge exchange to address challenges related to tourism, climate change, and talent attraction. The program involves 15 local authorities from Canada, Finland, Greenland, Iceland, Norway, Sweden, and the USA (EEAS, 2025).

We plan to deepen all contacts indicated above in the coming months, with the concrete hope to see the first concrete uses of the INFRA higher levels (at least Level 1) during the fire season 2026. Among actions devoted to accomplishing that there's also a trip to Canada planned before the end of 2025.

In addition to webinars, promoting INFRA at conferences is also part of the strategy, the next important event being for sure the Arctic Circle Assembly in October 2025. In light of this, a specific session was proposed there in collaboration with the AURORAE air quality forecast service. The proposal was accepted. The session will offer a very important opportunity not only to develop existing contacts but also to foster new ones.

What has been reported so far includes a very important element that deserves further exploration: the connection we have been trying to build over the past two years between the INFRA fire service and the AURORAE air quality forecast service. Fires, which release large quantities of particles, particularly carbonaceous particles, and other gaseous compounds, are a significant source of short-lived climate forcers (SLCFs). There is growing concern about the impact on air quality that the increase in fires brought about by climate change could have. Large fires release large quantities of particles and gases visible even to satellites, which can be transported over great distances, dramatically reducing local visibility. The effects on the respiratory systems of humans and wildlife are less visible but certainly much more dangerous. The macroscopic phenomena of smoke and poor visibility make the connection between these two issues clear even to non-experts. They also lead to a strong user demand for the combination of information, which, however, is still poorly available in a single service. Above all, once again there is a lack of attention to transforming information and predictions into simple and clear messages for non-experts. At the moment, our integration plan involves AUROARE service developing a Wildfire module that transfers the following datasets to the INFRA service on daily basis via an HTTPS/FTPS service:

- CAMS forecast of PM10 fraction emitted by wildfires
- Flux of total PM10 emitted by wildfires

The CAMS forecasts of PM10 fraction emitted by wildfires are released at daily frequency by 9 models of CAMS, as for the PM10 CAMS forecast, and will be downloaded with daily frequency at 08:00 UTC for the current day ($t=0$) and for the following 48h ($t=2$) (CAMS, 2025) by the AURORAE automatic procedure.

The wildfire flux of total PM ($\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) is released at daily frequency at 07:00 UTC by the CAMS global biomass burning emissions based on fire radiative power (GFAS) that assimilates fire radiative power (FRP) observations from satellite-based sensors to produce daily estimates of biomass burning emissions. CAMS GFAS data includes: FRP, dry matter burnt and biomass burning emissions (CAMS, 2025). The wildfire flux of total PM will be downloaded every day as a single netCDF file that covers the whole globe.

With a view to providing easily readable information, we are trying to understand what information and services are currently used by potential stakeholders, and how information on the second CAMS parameter can be passed through INFRA-AEGIS. Indeed, while the model output reproduces a continuous map similar to those associated with risk indices and weather fields, the emitted flux, assessed from satellite observations, is by its nature discontinuous and punctual. This may be highly relevant at the local level, but its representation in a format readable by a non-expert is by no means trivial. The information currently available in the GWIS service can help us understand the problem.

9. Final remarks in a legacy perspective

The previous sections report on the work carried out over the past two years and describe the current state of development of the INFRA service. Compared to the initial objectives, in line with other services developed within Arctic PASSION, INFRA's development has also moved beyond the

pilot phase. The multilevel approach allowed us to broaden the range of potential users, prioritizing individual use by non-experts. Local scale focus has been strengthened, as well as the ability to implement and manage levels above 0 (the basic one) with limited resources. The broad flexibility in modulating the service, as well as the fact that the IT platforms are using open-source software and are web-based, make it possible to develop ad hoc implementations with minimal effort and to install the service in the most suitable locations, even remote from the area of interest and the users. This is perhaps the aspect we initially least expected to be able to achieve. Other developments that exceed initial plans include the interaction and initial integration of the INFRA service with the AURORAE air quality forecasting service, and the ability to take concrete steps to ensure the medium-long-term sustainability of the service. Level 0 and level 1 are operational and can be accessed from the dedicated page created on the PRA portal. Level 2 has currently been developed at the demonstrator level, but the next step in code development is already planned to have level 2 ready for operational activation.

Although the initial objectives have been achieved and, in some respects, even exceeded, several actions and activities are still planned

- Strengthen dialogue with stakeholders with the aim of activating operational uses of INFRA at level 1 by 2026. At the same time, promote greater awareness and use of level zero, including through the creation of access points in the Arctic (the first in collaboration with AINA at the KLRS).
- Complete the development of Level 2 of INFRA until it has an operational version that can serve as a basis for specific implementations. Resolve remaining small inconsistencies and instabilities for Level 0 (for example, expand the offering of maps on which to project layers, a set reduced by the sudden closure of some Microsoft services). Improve and expand the documentation, also taking into account the suggestions and feedback that users wish to leave. In particular, create a small library of use cases.
- Contact services other than GWIS, in particular the Canadian CWFIS and the American National Interagency Fire Center, to explore how, through specific agreements, the information available on INFRA can be enriched, particularly for levels 1 and 2. The only important limitation, to always and only interact with well-certified public sources.
- Fully develop interaction with the AURORAE service, including information layers on fire emissions, particularly those from CAMS GFAS. We should also explore broader synergies on air quality, including the use of INFRA's capabilities to transfer information beyond fire emissions.

The actions listed above, subject to available means and resources, will continue even after the end of Arctic PASSION, enhancing the legacy of the Arctic PASSION project with regard to the INFRA service.

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